

Spiritual And Ethical Bases Of Forming A Sense Of Military Patriotism In Youth

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the moral and moral foundations of forming a sense of military patriotism in young people, as well as thoughts and opinions on love for the motherland and protection of the motherland.*

Keywords — homeland, patriotism, spirituality, methodological, national idea, spiritual-ethical, social-political, scientific-theoretical, national-spiritual, national pride.

INTRODUCTION.

As a proof that the issue of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism in our country has risen to the level of state policy, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "Educating and educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism and respect for our spiritual and moral values is completely foreign to our people. The issues of protection from destructive ideas were not paid enough attention.[1]"

Today, it is necessary to enjoy the spiritual heritage created in the past and the bravery of military commanders in the education of our youth in all aspects. Through deep study and understanding of the great national spirituality and moral foundations of our people and its history, it is necessary to serve our holy Uzbekistan towards the sole goal of our youth, who are considered the future of our country. Today, the most urgent task before our country is to preserve independence, to preserve the peace and tranquility of our people.[2]

It should be noted that in the context of globalization, threats to the human heart and mind are increasing. In particular, the increase in external influences, pressures, aggressions, and the escalation of information attacks are of serious concern to the world community. Currently, the increasing danger situation in the world requires us to be always alert, alert and alert.[3]

Military patriotism in young people is a feeling that shows high morality, and its content is strengthened by direct and indirect responsibility for the protection of the Motherland, its security and integrity. That is why true military patriotism requires putting the family above the family, the Motherland above the family, and humanity above the Motherland. The important thing is that the feelings in him do not fit into the narrow circle of patriotism, they "go beyond" it. Military patriotism is not limited to love or admiration for the Motherland, but is manifested in the mobilization of all strength and intelligence to solve problems related to the protection of the Motherland.[4]

In general, the essence of military patriotism seems to be embodied in this definition. However, it should be noted that civil patriotism is a system of knowledge about legal culture and obedience to the law, consisting in assessing the novelty of political and legal phenomena in society and the state, owning a civil position, always being ready in service to his people and fulfilling his constitutional duty.[5]

In history, the absorption of the courage of our national heroes such as our great compatriots Shiroq, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Najmiddin Kubro, Amir Temur and Babur into the minds of our youth, who fought valiantly against the enemy on the path of freedom of the land, independence, plays an important role in strengthening the sense of Homeland and forming a sense of patriotism.

Including glorifying the military patriotism of our great-grandfathers as a moral ideal, analyzing resources that reflect their moral views and Deeper Life activities related to patriotic virtue, such as Spitamen, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Najmiddin Kubro, Temur Malik, Amir Temur, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, will serve to further elevate military patriotism in young people.[6]

Military patriotism is a special type and integral part of National, national patriotism, which becomes even more important in the context of strengthening the state independence of Uzbekistan. Therefore, the study, research and analysis of the methodological foundations, scientific and theoretical features of military patriotism always remains an urgent moral issue.

The role and importance of military patriotism in the upbringing of young people in the spirit of a national idea, the upbringing of military patriotism depends not only on ideological grounds, but also on social, economic, political, moral ones. After all, although today military patriotic education is carried out directly through the system of the Armed Forces, the military sphere, state bodies and public organizations, the family, neighborhood and educational institution are in charge of its indirect implementation, and in this regard, every citizen should be well versed in national-spiritual and moral aspects.[3]

The basis of military patriotism is determined by the peace of the land. The main condition and guarantee of this methodology is to increase the power of our armed forces in today's threatening times, to further deepen the processes of modernization of our national army, to strengthen the defense capabilities of our country, to preserve the inviolability of the borders of our motherland as a guard of sight.

In the National-spirituality and moral values of the Uzbek people, military patriotism is valued as a virtue inherent in individuals who are able to show a deep respect for the history of the country, fate, examples of self-sacrifice in the path of Defense of the motherland. This feeling is one of the philosophical concepts that has not lost its position throughout the periods, even because it is formed on the basis of spiritual and moral concepts such as "love", "trust", "loyalty" and has a deep place in the hearts of people.[6]

Patriotism is glorified in all sources relating to the spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people, as it embodies such moral qualities as unification, orientation, chipsification, mobilization. Islam, which is considered our high spiritual value, is no exception.

In the socio-philosophical analysis of the role and importance of military patriotism in educating young people in the spirit of a national idea, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the upbringing of military patriotism depends not only on ideological grounds, but also on social, economic, political, moral ones. In this regard, it is advisable to expand the scope of educational work related to the study of the scientific and theoretical foundations of military patriotism. Such activities take an important place in the preparation of cadets and future young officers as true patriots.[5]

As a conclusion, we can say that today the young generation's thoughts about the motherland and its future, feeling a sense of patriotism, first of all: in connecting personal interests with the interests of the motherland; in the strength of national pride and a sense of national pride; in showing dedication towards the prosperity of the motherland; are clearly manifested in.

References

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